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Temporal and spatial changes in the environmental lapse rate distribution over the Arctic

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Temporal and spatial changes in the environmental lapse rate distribution over the Arctic

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E-mail: ci21923@bristol.ac.uk**Keywords:** environmental lapse rate, near surface temperature, Greenland, ArcticSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)**Abstract**

The Environmental Lapse Rate (ELR) depicts how the temperature near the surface varies with altitude and can be used for temperature downscaling coarse resolution data and for understanding boundary layer processes. We calculated the ELR using ERA5 reanalysis data, examined its temporal and larger-scale spatial variability, and found a prevalent seasonal ELR cycle over the Arctic. There are extensive positive ELR values resulting from pervasive inversions over most of the Arctic in winter; hence, we also explored the possible factors that lead to inversions in polar regions. Our results can serve as a reference for future research on the inversions in different morphological regions at different pressure levels. By improving the characterization of the ELR, we obtain a more explicit representation of the vertical temperature variation across the Arctic region and examine potential trends in ELR over time. Our results challenge the commonly assumed fixed ELR values that are typically used in the Arctic region in, for example, correcting ice-core temperature reconstructions or estimating higher-resolution runoff from land ice.

1. Introduction

The temperature near the surface varies with altitude, according to the environmental lapse rate (ELR). Hence, ELR has been applied to downscale global temperature reanalysis and climate projections in different complex terrain regions [1]. The ELR values are often assumed to be close to the theoretical adiabatic lapse rate of -6 to -7 °C km⁻¹ (e.g [2]). The mean free-air lapse rate -6.5 K km⁻¹ is commonly employed in downscaling, extrapolation of surface temperature, and paleoaltimetry studies [1, 3–5], because the free air lapse rate represents temperature changes along a vertical profile through the boundary layer and indicates broad-scale atmospheric stability [6]. However, it is not reasonable to use a fixed ELR value for large areas without considering the spatiotemporal variability, as the ELR changes seasonally and diurnally [3, 6], and is affected by factors such as the underlying surface types, topography, overlying

air masses, and ambient weather conditions such as wind and cloud cover [7].

Adopting a fixed free air lapse rate may result in significant estimation errors, yet there is still no consensus or definitive estimates for the ELR over the Greenland Ice Sheet (GrIS) and the wider Arctic region, which comprises extensive glaciated and permafrost areas. The GrIS has experienced accelerated melting [8], with an average mass loss rate of 268 Gt yr⁻¹ of the period 2002–2020 [9]. This rapid melting has significantly contributed to sea-level rise over the last two decades and is expected to continue in the future [10, 11–14]. Improved knowledge of the surface mass balance (SMB) over Greenland [15] is required to predict future mass loss. However, in the absence of comprehensive in-situ observations of SMB [11], regional climate models (RCMs) are used to derive SMB estimates [16–18]. Statistically downscaling SMB from the current RCM resolution, ranging from 5 to 20 km [19], to a 1 km resolution

can significantly reduce biases arising from coarse resolution [11]. In this process, ELR can be employed to statistically downscale the air temperature, as it reflects how the temperature varies with elevation [20].

The limited horizontal and vertical station coverage makes it nearly impossible to capture the spatial patterns of temperature variability across the pan-Arctic region. This is a region, however, where the ELR is crucial for the extrapolation from meteorological stations to different elevations and for providing empirical relationships between surface temperature and elevation, which are frequently exploited to aid in interpolating station data to create gridded fields [21, 22]. Understanding temporal or spatial variations in the ELR could improve downscaling and extrapolation in specific areas, such as Greenland, thus enhancing the understanding and precise modelling of SMB and other glacier and ice sheet processes [23].

Previous evaluations of the ELR over Greenland have relied on in-situ data from various stations, such as coastal met stations run by the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) or inland automatic weather stations [24]. However, not all sectors of Greenland are equally represented by in-situ data because the distribution of stations is uneven and sparse [24, 25]. One approach is to estimate the lapse rate derived from two stations at different altitudes [24] as an alternative to ELR. Nevertheless, this method needs to interpolate temperature data from sites at different locations to a standard latitude, which has been pointed out may produce artificial errors in extrapolation [3]. Another widely used alternative to the ELR in Greenland is the linear regression of temperature and altitudes of multiple stations [3, 6, 24, 26], which is the slope lapse rate. This lapse rate is predominantly driven by mountain processes [26] and may fail to reflect vertical variations in temperature. Furthermore, most stations begin in 1990 or later with a duration of ten years or less and frequently discontinuous or missing observations, making it challenging to identify a secular trend in the ELR using station data alone. As only limited data are available, obtained over different periods and sometimes for only a few months, the climatological mean ELR is difficult to estimate [27]. Research related to the air temperature on the surface in Greenland and other Arctic regions also remains limited. A thorough investigation of long-term and large-scale ELR in the pan-Arctic region has not yet been conducted.

Gao compared fixed monthly lapse rates, measured ELR and values derived from ERA-Interim reanalysis data in the German and Swiss Alps, and found that the ELR derived from pressure levels of ERA-Interim reanalysis data performs well for downscaling [20]. This methodology reduced the bias in the original ERA-Interim data and has

also been tested over the Tibetan Plateau [28] and other complex terrains [29]. With the update of European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis data to ERA5, the results derived from a similar methodology applied to the western US region showed that the temporally and spatially varying ELR derived from ERA5 vertical profiles provides the best temperature correction with elevation by removing most of the error dependence on altitude [1]. Based on this method, we investigate the spatio-temporal variations of ELR across the pan-Arctic, utilizing ERA5 reanalysis temperature data on pressure levels. Our primary focus is to investigate the long-term and large-scale variations in the ELR over the pan-Arctic land area. We also compared the ELR of the surface with the commonly used free-air level in the atmosphere. This comparison is important to extrapolate the vertical temperature over the pan-Arctic region.

This study covers the entire Arctic region, including sub-Arctic America, Eurasia, the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, and Greenland. Moreover, we compared the ELR derived from ERA5 data and NCEP reanalysis data with the results obtained from Greenland stations. We investigate the factors influencing ELR values over the area of interest. Our study integrates and discusses low-level inversions across the pan-Arctic during winter, which have traditionally been overlooked in previous lapse rate studies and are often separated from estimates of the ELR. This addresses a significant research gap related to neglecting positive ELR values [1]. By elucidating the spatial and temporal characteristics of the ELR, we fill the gap in understanding the ELR over the Arctic. Our study provides the vertical variations of free air to near-surface temperatures in the Arctic, which holds significance for reconstructing the paleoclimate from ice cores taken from Greenland that need to be corrected for elevation changes.

2. Data and method

2.1. Data

The data used for ELR calculations are the ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis ERA5 hourly and monthly averaged data on pressure levels from 1979 to the present, and the surface pressure (SP) data from ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1959 to the present. Given that the Arctic has been warming four times faster than the global mean over the last 40 years [30], it is expected that this could introduce a temporal trend in the ELR. Therefore, we investigated the ELR from 1980 to 2020 to assess whether secular trends were present. ERA5 is the fifth-generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past four to seven decades. ERA5 data are on regular latitude-longitude grids at 0.25×0.25 resolution with atmospheric parameters on 37 pressure levels.

Our analysis utilizes pressure levels from 500 hPa to 1000 hPa and the geopotential height and temperature at these levels. We also included similar ELR research utilizing the NCEP/DOE AMIP-II Reanalysis (Reanalysis-2) data to reduce the bias from ERA5.

As an independent test of our findings, we also incorporated the monthly mean temperature and geopotential height data from the Integrated Global Radiosonde Archive (IGRA) obtained from the National Centers for Environmental Information. This dataset comprises observations from radiosondes and pilot balloons collected from over 2800 stations worldwide.

2.2. Method of calculating the ELR

Gao *et al* obtained lapse rates in the Alps with four slightly different methods, and the result derived from the pressure levels of the ERA-Interim atmospheric reanalysis gave a better performance compared to the station data [20]. Therefore, we calculate the ELR based on the equation below, following Gao *et al* [20] and Dutra *et al* [1], but here using ERA5 reanalysis data:

$$\Gamma = \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta z} \quad (1)$$

where Γ is the lapse rate (K km^{-1}) of a grid point, Δz is the vertical distance between two selected pressure-level pairs, and ΔT is the temperature difference between the selected pressure levels.

We chose pressure levels as illustrated in the Supplementary Information. Based on the climatology of SP for each grid, we first obtained pressure values 50 hPa above the average SP (SP-50). We regarded the nearest upper ERA5 pressure level to this pressure as level A, along with the next 50 hPa level (level B) as the corresponding pressure level pairs (A and B) for calculating the ELR of each grid. For reference, refer to figure S.1 in the supplementary information, which illustrates the ERA pressure values used in the ELR calculations.

The 50 hPa geopotential height difference ensures that most of the time, the reference pressure level we will use is above the surface, considering that the multi-year standard deviation of SP is no more than 10 hPa. 50 hPa is a tradeoff between the availability and feasibility of the data and the ELR methodologies adopted in the past, and this ELR is closer to the free-air lapse rate, since the mountain's temperature differences depend primarily on the nearby free-air temperature [31]. We also performed surface-level ELR calculations in Greenland by adopting the nearest ERA5 pressure level to the SP level, and compared the surface-ELR with the 50 hPa ELR defined above. The surface-ELR represents the ELR at the surface, which is subject to substantial boundary layer effects. This will involve exceptional and infrequent

scenarios where the selected levels fall below the physical surface. In these cases, the 'below surface' temperatures, obtained through interpolation, have been verified to be valid despite their non-physical geopotential height.

3. Results

3.1. Temporal and spatial variability and trend in ELR over Greenland

We estimated the variation in Greenland's monthly averaged free-air and surface ELR from 1980 to 2020, as shown in figure 1(a). A distinct annual cycle is consistently presented in each year's data, whether at the surface or in the free air. For free-air ELR, high (absolute) monthly mean ELR values occur during summer, peaking at approximately -5.5 K km^{-1} , with the highest values typically observed in June. Conversely, low (absolute) values of Greenland ELR were observed during winter, with minima ranging from -3 to -2.5 K km^{-1} , predominantly occurring in February, the month with the lowest average temperature in Greenland. The range of free-air monthly ELR values of Greenland for each year lies within -2 to -5.5 K km^{-1} . A similar seasonal cycle exists in the Greenland surface ELR, with the main difference in the values. During summer, the highest (absolute) average surface ELR over Greenland is less than 4 K km^{-1} . In winter, most monthly ELR values over Greenland are positive. In addition, the amplitude of the seasonal variation is larger, reaching up to 4 K km^{-1} , whereas for the free-air ELR seasonal cycle, this amplitude is less than 2.5 K km^{-1} . In a word, we consider this annual cycle of Greenland's ELR to be a stable characteristic because it appears to be unaffected by recent warming trends. This conclusion was further validated after conducting a similar Greenland ELR analysis using NCEP Reanalysis-2 data, as shown in Supplementary Information.

The climatology of free-air ELR over Greenland generally falls in the range of -3 to -6 K km^{-1} , with the blue area covering south and central Greenland shown in figure 1(b). The smallest absolute free-air ELR values occurred mainly in northern Greenland. The somewhat discontinuous ELR pattern observed over Greenland results from the effects caused by the step change in pressure levels provided by ERA5 (25 or 50 hPa between adjacent levels), as explained in the supplementary information.

We also investigated the spatiotemporal evolution of free-air ELRs in Greenland by plotting the latitudinal averages against time. The annual cycle of the Greenland ELR and its seasonal variations are also shown in figure 2. Positive ELRs predominantly occur at higher latitudes during winter, specifically from December to February. These positive values are primarily north of Greenland (above 83.5° N) in the

Figure 1. (a): The multi-year monthly averaged Greenland's ELR on surface and free-air levels. The red line is the multi-year monthly averaged Greenland's surface ELR. The purple line is the multi-year monthly averaged Greenland's free air ELR, and the red, semi-transparent shading represents the range of monthly average free-air ELR values of Greenland from 1980 to 2022. (b): spatial distribution of Greenland ELR climatology from 1980 to 2022 using ERA5 data. The filled color is the 1980–2022 averaged free-air ELR; the -5 and -3 K km⁻¹ isolines are also plotted in black.

Figure 2. Free-air ELR variation with time (every 5 years from 1980 to 2020) and latitude over Greenland and the Arctic Ocean. The color is the longitude and monthly averaged ELR value and the 0 isolines are emphasized in bold in the figure. The x-axis represents the time from 1980 to 2020, with intervals of 5 years. The 'July' labels in the x-axis correspond to July of each labeled year (e.g. 1980.7, 1985.7, etc), indicating the summer period.

Arctic Ocean, with some also occurring in the margin of northern Greenland. Additionally, the absolute values of ELR over Greenland generally decreased with latitude in most months, except for June and July, when the spatial distribution of ELR in northern, southern, and central Greenland exhibited a relatively uniform pattern. It can be inferred that the overall ELR in Greenland does not vary significantly with latitude and lies around -5 K km⁻¹ during the summer.

3.2. Temporal and spatial variability in ELR of the pan-Arctic excluding Greenland

The topography of the land surrounding the central Arctic is generally flat, encompassing the northern regions of North America and Eurasia, which reduces the mean SP fluctuation caused by dramatic elevation

change, mitigating the marginal effect, as mentioned in the ELR spatial distribution over Greenland.

SubArctic North America and Northern Eurasia monthly average ELRs exhibit similar annual cycles of free-air ELR as seen in Greenland, as shown in figure 3. The monthly ELR values over these two areas reached their maximum (absolute) values in summer and gradually decreased from summer to winter. The highest (absolute) ELR values in summer were approximately -6 K km⁻¹ for subArctic North America and Northern Eurasia. The monthly mean ELR for both sub-Arctic North America and Northern Eurasia did not show a clear trend over the years. The primary difference between subArctic American and Northern Eurasian ELRs lies in the duration and magnitude of winter ELR values.

Figure 3. (a): Variation in subarctic North America monthly average ELR for each of the five years 1980–2020 (b): variation in Northern Eurasia monthly average ELR for each of the five years 1980–2020.

Figure 4. The climatological distribution of pan-Arctic ELR in January (left) and June (right). The filled color represents the multi-year averaged January (left) and June (right) free-air ELR over the pan-Arctic region. The white line in the diagram marks the ELR isolines of -6 and 0 K km^{-1} .

ELR (absolute) values below -4 K km^{-1} in Eurasia last considerably longer than those in subArctic America. In Eurasia, ELR (absolute) values below -4 K km^{-1} persist from May to September, whereas in North America, the same range of ELR is limited from June to August. This discrepancy results in a notably more prolonged winter pattern in subArctic America, where, even by March, the average ELR value remains positive, while in northern Eurasia, it is negative.

The pan-Arctic region, including Greenland and the Arctic Ocean, exhibits distinct seasonal variations in the ELR values. We observed significant differences by directly comparing the multi-year mean ELR in January (winter) and June (summer), as figure 4 shows. Negative ELR values are prevalent in summer across most pan-Arctic land areas; over northern Eurasia and subArctic America, the ELR values could even be lower than -6 K km^{-1} , indicating a highly stable and potentially stratified atmosphere during the summer months. Conversely, extensive regions with positive ELR values dominate during winter in northern Eurasia and North America.

In contrast to land areas, the Arctic Ocean consistently exhibits positive ELR values throughout the year, with slightly higher absolute values observed during winter.

3.3. Validation with station data over the Greenland

There are 13 stations of IGRA 2.2 Greenland, but only 10 of these have temperature and pressure data to be used for calculating ELRs. We use the same pressure level pairs (50 hPa above the surface) for each station at the nearest ERA-5 grid point. Nonetheless, only five stations have a complete time series of temperature and geopotential height from 1980 to 2020 and are available for the following analysis. We found robust spatial variance in the monthly mean ELR variation of these stations (see in supplementary information). The monthly ELR values of the northernmost station DANMARKSHAVN (station number: GLM00004320) fluctuated dramatically; positive ELR values occurred quite often in both winter and spring/autumn seasons, while ELR of the southernmost station MITTARFIK (station number:

GLM00004270) were between -4 and -7 K km^{-1} and remained within this range regardless of season. The comparison of the ELRs of these two stations supports the spatial variation of the Greenland ELR, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 5 demonstrates the spatial distribution of IGRA stations throughout Greenland, with annotated red labels indicating the index number of each station and the corresponding station ELR in table 1. The station results were also compared with ERA5-derived ELRs by superimposing the climatology of ERA5 free-air ELRs on the background, and we observed a similarity in the spatial distribution of the two-method ELRs. However, due to the low temporal completeness of the station data, it is difficult to use the station data further to verify the temporal variation pattern of the ELR over a larger scale. As shown in table 1, the differences between most (time complete) station-ELR and ERA5-ELR are less than 0.5 K km^{-1} , except for station ITTOQQORTOORMIIT (station number: GLM00004339), whose nearest ERA5 grid point is located in the ocean according to the ERA5 land mask. Because the inversion layer over the ocean is thicker than on land [30], the ELR in the ocean will be significantly disturbed, making these two values not comparable.

4. Discussion

The monthly averaged ELRs over the pan-Arctic region show a similar seasonal variation pattern. Notably, the spatially averaged free-air ELR over the entire pan-Arctic region is at most -6 K km^{-1} (-4 K km^{-1} for surface ELR), which is much smaller than both the historical result range and the commonly used constant lapse rate (-6.5 K km^{-1}).

The most crucial factor that made our results differ from previous ELR research is that we included positive ELR values in our averaged results instead of discarding them [1], as previous work tends to do [23]. The climatology of free-air ELR in northeastern Greenland was lower than -3 K km^{-1} , where the inversions occurred most frequently and at their strongest [32]. We believe that the positive ELR values in winter over the pan-Arctic region shown in our results, mainly caused by inversions [32], should not be ignored.

Inversions occur when the coldest and densest air settles to the lowest topographic level [33] and air temperature inversions are a common feature of Arctic coastal areas [25, 34–37]. Inversions also appeared on the Antarctic coast [38] and over the ice-covered sea [39]. Various near-surface factors, including clouds [40, 41], topography, and wind [42], could heavily influence near-surface temperature, making inversions fairly persistent and predominant over the pan-Arctic region [35, 37, 43, 44]. Two types of inversions have been investigated in the Arctic: surface-based inversions (SBI) and elevated inversions [32, 35–37]. Elevated inversions are considered to be those above ground level and may develop as remnants of SBI. In winter, on the Arctic coast, SBIs are frequently based up to 200 m above the surface, and the inversion layer depth changes dramatically and can reach up to 800 m [37], which is strong enough to disturb the near-surface temperature, making it nearly impossible to obtain a stable lapse rate at ground level.

The climatology of Greenland surface ELR spatial distribution in the Supplementary Information shows a much larger area of positive ELR compared to the free-air Greenland ELR. These extensive positive ELRs indicate the occurrence of strong

Table 1. The information of Greenland IGRA stations. The station number and name, data time completeness, station locations, nearest ERA5 grid point, and multi-year mean ELR values are in this table.

Number in figure	Station number	Station name	Data complete	Lon of station	Lat of station	Lon in ERA-5	Lat in ERA-5	Selected pressure level pairs in ERA5	Station mean ELR (K/km)	ERA-5 mean ELR (K/km)
1	GLM00004202	PTTUFFIK	Up to 2006	-68.75	76.53	-68.75	76.5	900-850	-4.02	-3.55
2	GLM00004220	AASIAAT	Time complete	-52.85	68.71	-52.75	68.75	925-875	-4.05	-3.78
3	GLM00004231	KANGERLUSSUAK	1947-1948	-50.80	67.00	-50.75	67	900-850	—	-4.30
4	GLM00004270	MITTARFIK	Time complete	-45.42	61.17	-45.5	61.25	875-825	-5.14	-4.81
5	GLM00004310	NORD	Only 1972	-16.67	81.60	-16.75	81.5	900-850	—	-0.59
6	GLM00004320	DANMARKSHAVN	Time complete	-18.67	76.77	-18.75	76.75	925-875	-1.95	-1.23
7	GLM00004339	ITTOQQORTOORMIIT	Time complete	-21.95	70.48	-22	70.5	925-875	-3.77	-1.34
8	GLM00004340	KAP	Up to 1980	-21.97	70.42	-22	70.5	925-875	-3.85	-1.34
9	GLM00004360	TASIIIAQ	Time complete	-37.64	65.61	-37.75	65.5	925-875	-4.84	-4.45
10	GLM00004417	GEOSUMMIT	From 2012	-38.46	72.58	-38.5	72.5	600-550	-6.65	-5.13

SBI over Greenland, especially during the winter [44]. Focusing on the surface level means that the ELR we determine is dominated by boundary layer effects. Consequently, we prefer to use levels that are closer to the free-air ELR (50 hPa above the surface, which is approximately 500 m altitude) to investigate the temporal and spatial variability of the vertical temperature profile over the pan-Arctic, which could ensure that in most months and most areas, ELR values are stable and negative. The 50 hPa level we chose was a tradeoff between looking for more apparent ELR temporal-spatial characteristics over the pan-Arctic and having stable reference values.

Although we want to eliminate the potentially dominating influence of SBIs by elevating the computation levels slightly, our results still show positive ELR values and are affected by strong low-level inversions in winter. To verify that retaining these positive

values in our temporally and spatially averaged ELR results is reasonable, we investigated the detailed temperature vertical profiles of grid points exhibiting abnormal positive ELR values. The vertical distance between the two selected pressure levels (represented as Δz in equation (1)) remains relatively unchanged over time when an inversion occurs at a point. It is the reversed temperature difference between the two levels that determines a positive ELR value, indicating the occurrence of an inversion. We selected an ERA5 grid (81° N, 16° W) on the margin of Greenland and near a DMI Station, Nord (station number: 4312; location: $81^{\circ}36'N$, $16^{\circ}39'W$), as an example to show inversions.

The ‘Inversion box’ in figure 6(b) shows that although we try to avoid SBIs, relative higher-level inversions do occur within the pressure levels used, and this inversion could be an extension or remnant

of SBI, reflecting the near-surface temperature vertical change. To accurately represent the vertical temperature distribution over the research area, we included these positive values in our ELR calculation to present a more realistic representation of the real-world ELR. Combined with our previous surface GrIS ELR results, we also found that the ELR of a single point in Greenland may be sensitive to pressure, geopotential height, local wind and cloud [40], or any other near-surface processes and seasonal cycle pattern.

Because there is an ELR annual cycle and Arctic-scale spatial distribution, the presence of inversions in the pan-Arctic region in our results also exhibits corresponding temporal and spatial variability [31]. The snow cover in the northern part of Greenland was reduced in July and returned in September [45], which aligns with the timing of the inversions observed in our results and other research on inversions over Greenland [44]. Extensive positive ELR values over Northern Eurasia, mainly in Siberia, only occur during winter (usually from November to March), which nearly coincides with the duration of maximum ice and snow cover in Eurasia [46]. In most pan-Arctic regions, the temporal variation in snow cover is consistent with the occurrence of inversions, as shown in the supplementary information figures.

The extensive inversions over the pan-Arctic area in winter are likely attributed to the combined effect of the cold and dry atmosphere, relatively few clouds, and the cold snow surface, making low-level inversions very frequent, persistent, and intense during this season [44, 45]. We compared the seasonal cycles of various meteorological variables and found that only surface cloud cover and surface snow cover exhibit similar seasonal cycles to the ELR in our research. Snow cover plays a more significant role in low-level inversions because spatial and temporal variations in snow cover closely correspond to seasonal changes in the ELR over the pan-Arctic land area. It has been proven that snow cover in Siberia and northern Canada can induce intense surface cooling with subsidence, contributing to the formation of inversions [47].

5. Conclusion

We used ERA5 temperature reanalysis data to obtain the pan-Arctic free-air ELR values and add more interpretation to the surface Greenland ELR. All monthly averaged ELR values for Greenland exhibited a distinct seasonal cycle, with the free-air ELR ranging from -2 to -6 K km⁻¹ and peaking during summer. The surface Greenland ELR showed a similar seasonal cycle, but with lower absolute values. Similarly, the free-air ELR values over the other pan-Arctic land areas followed an annual cycle with higher (absolute) values near -6 K km⁻¹ during summer, gradually

decreasing from summer to winter, and showing positive ELR values in winter. Different regions may differ on the 'summer value' time and the magnitude of winter averaged ELR. Various factors, including latitude, topography, sea ice, and snow cover, influence the spatial distribution of pan-Arctic ELR. Unlike the whole-year persistent SBIs, low-level inversions are only common over the pan-Arctic winter and are more significantly affected by snow cover in the polar region. To reduce the uncertainty from ERA5, we conducted same analysis over Greenland with NCEP2 and obtained same strong seasonal cycle. We also validated the spatial distribution of the ELR over Greenland using station data and found that our ELR calculation performed well over land.

One important conclusion from our analysis is how ice core data are corrected for elevation changes in paleoclimatic reconstructions. Paleoclimate reconstructions of past temperatures from ice cores in Greenland need to be corrected for changes in the elevation of the surface at the time the snow precipitated. Typically, these corrections have used a 'standard' lapse rate of 6 K km⁻¹ [48], which we show is an overestimation even in summer and about a factor of 2 too large in winter and potentially positive for the surface ELR (figure 1). This correction of ice cores has implications when attempting to reconstruct Holocene thinning over Greenland from multiple cores spread across the GrIS [49]. We suggest that care should be taken when making these corrections, and the assumption of a fixed theoretical lapse rate of 6 K km⁻¹ will lead to biases in the reconstructed temperature with elevation changes.

Our results covered 40 years, captured the seasonal cycle of ELR, and compared the multi-year monthly mean ELR values, contributing to an improved understanding of vertical temperature structures over the pan-Arctic region, especially over Greenland, which is crucial for the interpretation of synoptic-scale or larger-scale climatic processes in the Arctic. The ELR at different altitudes in Greenland can provide reference values for temperature downscaling at both the surface and free air levels. The discussion of extended inversions in the pan-Arctic region is a valuable reference for studying potential temperature variations and inversion phenomena in the Arctic. Further investigation of the lapse rate (and inversion) surface-type dependence, such as how the ELR varies over the ocean, is required. In our results, inversions are more robust and persistent over the ocean than over land throughout the year, and this difference may also require further discussion.

Data availability statement

ERA5 dataset is available from the Copernicus Climate Change Service: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-reanalysis>. The NCEP2 data link is

included in the supplementary information. IGRA data is available from: <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/weather-balloon/integrated-global-radiosonde-archive>.

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